

ON 2-PHENYL-4-AMINOQUINOLINE DERIVATIVES.

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Certain 2-phenyl-4-(dialkylamino-4'-sulphonamidophenyl-, and 4'-amidobenzene-sulphonyl-) aminoquinolines have been described. The yield of the condensation product is invariably poor.

The recent researches in chemotherapy have revealed that the dialkyl-aminoalkylamine chains play a considerable part in the development of the therapeutic activity in quinoline and acridine derivatives. Similarly sulphanilamide and its derivatives have been found to possess definite bacteriostatic action against various coccal infections. It was, accordingly, considered to be of interest to study the class of compounds formed by the fusion of the above groupings to the γ -position of 2-phenylquinoline, the 4-carboxyl derivative of which is also largely used in medicine. It may be mentioned that 2-phenyl-, and 2-phenyl-6-methoxy-4-(4'-aminobenzenesulphonyl)-aminoquinolines (I, R = H or MeO) are expected to have some therapeutic importance since the replacement of one hydrogen atom of sulphonamido group of *p*-aminobenzenesulphonamide often widens the range of activity of the drug (*cf.* Whitby, *Lancet*, 1937, *i*, 1517; 1938, *i*, 1210; Grütz, *Deut. Med. Woch.*, 1937 33, 1932; Domagk, *Klin. Woch.*, 1937, **16**, 1412).

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Phenyl-4-(β -diethylaminoethyl)-aminoquinoline.—A mixture of 2-phenyl-4-aminoquinoline (4.4 g.), prepared according to John (*Ber.*, 1926, **59**, 1448), diethylaminoethyl bromide (4 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) and a trace of copper powder in dry xylene was heated under reflux for 12 hours. The mixture was then extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid and the extract was rendered neutral to congo-red with potassium carbonate. It was then extracted with ether to remove any unchanged 2-phenyl-4-aminoquinoline and the aqueous portion was treated with excess of potassium carbonate when the product separated out as an oily mass. This was then dissolved

in ether, the ethereal solution dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate and ether removed and the residue distilled under reduced pressure. The portion boiling between $272-76^{\circ}/6$ mm., was collected. (Found : N, 13.2. $C_{21}H_{25}N_3$ requires N, 13.16 per cent). It is a viscous yellow liquid, n_D^{31} , 1.6510. The base readily forms an extremely hygroscopic hydrochloride and a picrate. The latter was crystallised from a large volume of alcohol in clusters of yellow needles, m.p. $238-39^{\circ}$. (Found : N, 16.08. $C_{21}H_{25}N_3$, $2C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 16.21 per cent).

2-Phenyl-4-(γ -diethylaminopropyl)-aminoquinoline.— 2-Phenyl-4-aminoquinoline and diethylaminopropyl chloride in molecular proportions were heated under reflux with potassium carbonate and copper in xylene for 24 hours. The product was isolated as described previously, b.p. $265-70^{\circ}/6$ mm. (Found : N, 12.7. $C_{22}H_{27}N_3$ requires N, 12.6 per cent). It is a yellow viscous liquid and forms a hygroscopic hydrochloride. The picrate separated from alcohol in fine yellow needles, m.p. 234° . (Found : N, 16.05. $C_{22}H_{27}N_3$, $2C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 15.93 per cent).

2-Phenyl-4-(δ -diethylaminobutyl)-aminoquinoline.— A mixture of 2-phenyl-4-chloroquinoline (1 part, Knorr and Fertig, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 938), diethylamino-*n*-butylamine (1 part) in dry amyl alcohol was heated at $110-20^{\circ}$ for 12 hours after the addition of potassium carbonate and copper powder. Amyl alcohol and the unreacted butylamine derivative were removed by steam, and the residual mass was treated with dilute acetic acid in which the chloroquinoline was insoluble. The acetic acid solution was then filtered and the filtrate was neutralised with potassium carbonate, and the whole was then extracted with ether. The ethereal solution on drying over anhydrous potassium carbonate was concentrated to a viscous mass. This was redissolved in dilute acetic acid and the process was repeated. The yield of the crude condensation product was poor and the substance was isolated as picrate which was recrystallised from alcohol in fine yellow microscopic needles, m.p. 203° . (Found : N, 15.74. $C_{23}H_{29}N_3$, $2C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 15.65 per cent). The base liberated from the picrate with alkali was extracted with ether. The residue from ether, dried over liquid paraffin and phosphorus pentoxide in *vacuo*, was a deep yellow thick liquid. (Found : N, 12.02. $C_{23}H_{29}N_3$ requires N, 12.1 per cent).

2-Phenyl-4-(δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoquinoline.— δ -Diethylamino- α -methylbutylamine on being heated with 2-phenyl-4-chloroquinoline at $150-60^{\circ}$ for 20 hours gave the phenylaminoquinoline derivative as a viscous mass. This was purified by dissolving in acetic acid and precipitating with potassium carbonate. This viscous mass gave a picrate, m.p. 162° , after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found : N, 15.75. $C_{24}H_{31}N_3$, $2C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 15.4 per cent).

2-Phenyl-6-methoxy-4-(γ-diethylaminopropyl)-aminoquinoline. — 2-Phenyl-6-methoxy-4-aminoquinoline, prepared from 6-methoxy-atophan as prescribed by John (*loc. cit.*) melted at 159°. (Found: N, 11.35. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 11.2 per cent). John and Lukas (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1931, *ii*, 130, 314) gave m.p. 143°.

The above quinoline (5 g.) and diethylaminopropyl chloride (3 g.) were heated together at 160-70° for 12 hours. It was then mixed with an aqueous solution of potassium carbonate (1.5 g.) and the whole was subjected to steam distillation for about 1 hour. The mixture was then cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was shaken with dilute hydrochloric acid and the acid extract was subsequently treated with excess of potassium carbonate. The heavy oil that separated out, was collected and purified in the usual way. It is a very high boiling thick liquid difficult to distil. The picrate of the compound crystallised from alcohol in fine yellow needles with greenish tinge, m.p. 185°. (Found: N, 15.46. $C_{23}H_{29}ON_3$, $2C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 15.35 per cent).

2-Phenyl-6-methoxy-4-(δ-diethylamino-n-butyl)-aminoquinoline. — 2-Phenyl-6-methoxy-4-chloroquinoline, m. p. 109° (*cf.* John and Lukas, *loc. cit.*), and diethylaminobutylamine in molecular proportions gave the condensation product as a deep yellow viscous mass. After purification by the usual method, the picrate was prepared as yellow needles, m.p. 192°, after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: N, 15.3. $C_{24}H_{31}ON_3$, $2C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 15.1 per cent).

2-Phenyl-4-(4'-sulphonamidophenyl)-aminoquinoline. — 2-Phenyl-4-chloroquinoline (2.4 g.) and *p*-aminobenzenesulphonamide (1.6 g.) were heated together with a little copper powder at 160-170° for 16 hours. The reaction mixture was dissolved in boiling alcohol, filtered, and cautiously basified with dilute ammonia. The solid was collected, washed with hot water and finally crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in fine, colourless needles, m. p. 250°. (Found: N, 11.29; S, 8.0. $C_{21}H_{18}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 11.17; S, 8.5 per cent).

2-Phenyl-4-(4'-sulphondiethylamidophenyl)-aminoquinoline. — 2-Phenyl-4-chloroquinoline (2 g.) and *p*-aminobenzenesulphondiethylamide (3 g.) under the above conditions (period of heating 10 hours) afforded the condensation product which crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 144°. (Found: N, 10.0. $C_{25}H_{25}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 9.8 per cent). It is more soluble in alcohol and is also moderately soluble in ether and benzene.

2-Phenyl-4-(4'-amidobenzenesulphonyl)-aminoquinoline. — 2-Phenyl-4-aminoquinoline dissolved in benzene was mixed with a solution of

4-acetaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride in benzene, and the mixture was subsequently heated under reflux for 4 hours. After standing overnight, the benzene solution was decanted off and the solid mass formed was dissolved in alcohol and the solution was then neutralised with dilute ammonia avoiding rise of temperature. The substance crystallised on scratching and was recrystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 297°. (Found : N, 10.34; S, 7.55. $C_{23}H_{19}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 10.07; S, 7.67 per cent). The substance is soluble in excess of ammonia and does not give a diazo reaction in the cold.

The above acetyl derivative (2 g.), dissolved in rectified spirit (20 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.16, 1.5 c. c.) was heated for 2 hours on the steam-bath. The solution was concentrated, cooled and just neutralised with dilute ammonia. 2-Phenyl-4-(4'-amidobenzenesulphonyl)-aminoquinoline slowly separated out and was crystallised from dilute alcohol in microscopic needles, m. p. 293°. (Found : N, 11.5. $C_{21}H_{17}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 11.2 per cent). The substance is soluble both in acids and alkalis and gives a diazo reaction.

2-Phenyl-6-methoxy-4-(4'-amidobenzenesulphonyl)-aminoquinoline.—2-Phenyl-6-methoxy-5-aminoquinoline and 4-acetaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride were separately dissolved in hot dimethylaniline, mixed and then heated in an oil-bath at 150° for 1 hour. The dimethylaniline was decanted off. The separated solid was dissolved in alcohol, treated with charcoal, filtered and basified with ammonia. On concentration, the solution afforded 2-phenyl-6-methoxy-4-(4'-acetaminobenzenesulphonyl)-aminoquinoline which was finally crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 268°. (Found : N, 9.27; S, 6.95. $C_{24}H_{21}O_4N_3S$ requires N, 9.4; S, 7.18 per cent). It is soluble in excess of ammonia and this ammoniacal solution on heating hydrolyses to 2-phenyl-6-methoxy-4-aminoquinoline, identified by mixed m. p.

The above acetaminobenzenesulphonyl derivative was dissolved in absolute alcohol (25 c. c.) and refluxed on a water-bath for 1 hour after adding 4 c. c. of 5*N*-hydrochloric acid. The solution was concentrated, cooled and just neutralised with ammonia. The crystals of 2-phenyl-6-methoxy-4-(4'-aminobenzenesulphonyl)-aminoquinoline were collected, washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 268°. (Found : N, 10.48. $C_{22}H_{19}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 10.37 per cent).